

2019 I-SPIE Conference

Explorations and Adventures: Mapping our Future

July 18 – 19, 2019 at CSU, Fullerton

Presentations

Keynote: Char Booth

Information privilege: Access, Advocacy, and the Critical Role of Libraries.

In the world of higher education and libraries, there is a growing awareness of widespread inequality in information access. Information privilege is the concept that some enjoy greater access to information than others based on a variety of sociocultural factors such as social class and institutional affiliation. Information privilege creates an inherent barrier to knowledge, yet libraries and librarians hold a fundamental value of open information - and no group within libraries is more aware of the constraints of information privilege than those who work in resource sharing. This keynote will examine the role of libraries in a complex information ecosystem, question the obligations we have to our communities to challenge information privilege, and offer strategies that libraries can pursue to facilitate greater information equity.

Presenter: David Walker

Now I Get It! Customizing and Simplifying the Get It Menu in Alma/Primo

Alma's display of physical holdings and related request options within the Primo 'Get It' menu is rather complex. It appears to be optimized for large research institutions, leaving other types of institutions with an interface that is not ideal for their (often simpler) needs. This presentation will showcase work by the Discovery UResolver Task Force to replace the Get It menu in Primo with one of our own design, providing a streamlined display of holdings and a simplified resource sharing request option. David will explain the problems our users faced with the default Alma UResolver interface, the group's exploration of options to improve the user experience, the work they did to implement this customization, and some considerations for the future.

Presenter: Meghann Brenneman

IDS Workflows at Humboldt

Review the IDS workflows and benefits of IDS implementation at Humboldt. An evaluation of the new and old workflow and the impact IDS may have at your library.

Presenters: Resource Sharing Functional Committee Members

ULMS Resource Sharing Functional Committee Overview

The RSFC will provide an overview of the projects and tasks that they have worked on during the prior year. Accomplishments, achievements and ongoing goals will be discussed. New members of the RSFC for the upcoming year will be introduced.

Presenter: Meghann Brenneman

ILL Data Resources and You

How to become an ILL data expert? Through a review of data assessment resources attendees will have what they need to bring their ILL data into conversations at their libraries.

Presenter: Mike Richins

Rapid ILL – Current Projects and Future Directions

This session will provide an update on RapidILL including current projects and future directions. We will look at RapidR – Returnables, and its ability to facilitate efficient monograph-sharing for both consortial and non-consortial Rapid partners using smart lender identification and custom routing. Information on Project Bedrock, a new ILL request management platform, will also be shared.

Presenters: Mark Bilby and Greg Witmer

What does Open Access Mean for the Future of Interlibrary Lending?

Open Access can mean a lot of things to a lot of people. On the technological side, it can simply mean immediate access to content—whether legally or not—via the internet, social media, or cell phones. On the legal side, it can refer to massive shifts happening in Open Access policies or big deal negotiations with publishers. 2020 is sizing up to be an especially pivotal year, as countries and universities are increasingly playing hardball through major OA initiatives such as OA2020 and Plan S.

What does all this mean for Interlibrary Lending going forward? As more and more content becomes not only digital, but also legally open and instantly accessible, how will this impact the role of Interlibrary Loans?

In this presentation, we will talk about currents in Open Access and their implications for Collection Development, Systems integration, Discovery Tools and Workflows, and even Information Literacy. What we envision is that Interlibrary Loan staff will be called to focus increasingly on user-service and interaction, and in the process will have a myriad of

opportunities to be advocates and transformational agents who make academic information open.

Presenter: Tony Landolt

Article Galaxy Scholar - Your Collection Development Safety Net

The Article Galaxy Scholar Collection powered by Reprints Desk is tailored to help academic institutions supplement subscriptions and Interlibrary Loan (ILL) service to reduce spending and meet the immediate research needs of faculty and graduate students. Learn how Reprints Desk is making it easier for library staff to manage on-demand access for selected patrons or to specific journals while controlling spending and reducing manual mediation time.

Presenters: Joe Adkins and Allyce Ondricka

Reduce Your ILL Copyright Fees

Everybody has to pay ILL copyright fees. But have you ever wished you could pay less on copyright fees so that your library could better spend the money elsewhere? If so, Joe Adkins and Allyce Ondricka will show you how to use a variety of tools including Open Access and comparison shopping to reduce your ILL copyright fees.

Presenters: Ann Roll and Mike De Mars

A floating collection for the CSU, one step further toward collaborative collection development and management

Thanks to the options provided by the ULMS implementation and CSU+, the CSU is ready to explore further opportunities for collaboration. This presentation proposes the possibility of a floating collection for the CSU libraries. In a floating collection, individual items have no fixed home. When one CSU campus lends an item to a user at another CSU campus, upon the user's return of the item, the item would be shelved at the borrowing institution rather than being returned to the lending campus. This ensures that the books reside where they are being used but have the flexibility to relocate as needs change. The presentation will respond to the recommendations of the Systemwide Committee on Print Management (SCOPM) and will discuss the floating collection currently in place at the Pennsylvania State University system.

Presenter: Jenny Rosenfeld - OCLC

OCLC Resource Sharing Update

Learn about what's new with OCLC's resource sharing products – with a special focus on Tipasa and all the ways it now integrates with Alma. You'll hear about Tipasa's OPAC integration with Alma for availability and shelving location lookup as well as the NCIP Integration with Alma for circulation. OCLC partnered with several libraries to test this integration from December, 2018 – March, 2019 and then launched NCIP integration with Alma to all current and implementing Tipasa/Alma libraries in April of 2019. We will also review updated road maps to show you what to expect with OCLC's Resource Sharing products in the upcoming year.

Presenter: Ex Libris

Article Processing / Resource Sharing Next Gen Solution / Product Roadmap

Abstract forthcoming

Moderators: I-SPIE Conference Planning Committee

Future Directions of I-SPIE Discussion

Conference attendees will have the opportunity to discuss how I-SPIE can best help and serve the resources sharing community. Is I-SPIE's current charge still accurate and appropriate in our changing environment? Are all the I-SPIE committees still vital and necessary? What workflows and functions can I-SPIE focus on to help your library and the resource sharing community flourish?